

Investigating the impact of economic risks (depression, inflation, lowering the bank interest rates) on the sales of life insurances

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Abstract

The objective of the current research is to study the impact of economic risks (depression, inflation, lowering the bank interest rates) on the sales of life insurances where the economic risks are initially measured through ARCH-GARCH family models and then the intensity of the impact of the economic risks are examined and determined on the sales of life insurances. In this regard, the type of research was correlation-causal and in terms of the nature and time it is considered to be practical and cross-sectional, respectively. In this research, time series data were used on the economic risks and the sales of the life insurances and they were used for the time period 1971 through 2015. The results showed that: A) Based on instantaneous response functions, by creating a positive shock equal to one standard deviation in the economic risks, the percentage of the sales of life insurances starts to decrease from the first year. As a result, increases in the economic fluctuations lead to decreases in the sales of life insurances. B) Variance analysis functions show that variables of inflation rates, gross domestic product, and interest rate fluctuations account for 0.56%, 1.33%, and 2.1% of the error variance for the sales of life insurances, respectively. C) Economic risks (depression, inflation, lowering the band interest rates) have significant impacts on the sales of life insurances.

Keywords: Inflation risks, interest rate risk, gross domestic product risk, life insurance sales

1. Introduction

Insurance is considered as a major achievement in the developed human life. The importance of insurance in the modern human life is such that the governments pay great attention to it as well and try to show its true value in the economic and social aspects of people's lives by developing it through planning and policy-making. When the main source of income of the families is wasted due to the householder's early death, disability, unemployment, old age or retirement, in case no alternative sources of income exists, the family faces living difficulties. In this situation, life insurances are the tools which could create a minimum

supply for the families. Life insurance is considered as an important service in the insurance industry and plays its key role in determining and guaranteeing the future of the families. Today, under the coverage of life insurance, the people in developed countries have achieved proper conditions in terms of the risks of the death of the householder and its resultant economic issues as well as the issues due to the old age of the individuals. In these countries, life insurance largely contributes to the income of the society and through the obtained enormous financial resources, various services are provided for the members of the society. In developed countries, the insurance firms active in the field of life insurances have invested considerable financial resources in the financially profitable sectors and in a number of situations, they even offer a portion of the profit to those who are insured. In a number of developing countries, this industry is held by the governments due to the high volume of investments and the profit is added to the public income (Pajooyan et al., 2003:2). Personal insurances (Life, accidents, time period) are the known indicators for the measurement of the welfare of the people and the countries in which the people enjoy this welfare according to their needs, participate in the development planning of their society more confidently (Roje, 1999). The most important indicators for investigating the performance of the insurance industry include the amount and growth of the received insurance premiums, the ratio of the received insurance premiums to the gross domestic product, the per capita received insurance premium and claims ratio.

While the claims ratio refers to the efficiency and effectiveness of the insurance industry, other indicators are mostly important in terms of position and scope of the insurance industry. Insurance is able to play a key role in the social and economic development by creating a certainty in the collection of economic activities. Economic risks including inflation, interest rate, and economic depression could have an inhibitory role in the development of life insurance and the acceptance of this type of insurance. Economic risks including inflation might cause the investments in life insurances to have lower actual values at the time of the contract expiration compared to the beginning of the contract.

2. Literature review

Kojososki (2012) examined the effective factors on the demand of the life insurances in 14 central and south-eastern European countries using the fixed effects method (panel data model) in the period 1998-2010. The results of this research showed that the per capita gross domestic product, inflation, healthcare costs, education level, and the role of law are the strongest factors in the predictions for using life insurance. The real interest rate, controlling corruption and the effectiveness of the government do not seem to be highly effective on the demand of the life insurances in the central and south-eastern European countries.

Lee et al. (2007) addressed the analysis of the effective factors on the demand of the life insurance in 30 OECD countries during 1993-2000. The results of their research showed that the income, education level, and competition levels have a positive relationship with the demand of life insurance. The costs of social security, inflation, and the real interest rate decrease the demand for life insurance in OECD countries.

Diacon studied the life insurance demand in England in the period 1946-1968. The dependent variables of insurance, regular life insurance and explanatory variables of real inflation rate, real market value index, real permanent income, wealth, the number of children, marital status, income tax rate, unemployment rate, and changing rate of the unemployment rate were taken into account. The results of the research showed that the income elasticity of the demand for the savings-based insurance and for protection-based insurance were 3.5 and 2.5, respectively. The income tax rate has a significantly positive impact on the demand of the

life insurance in both models. The unemployment rate has a significant positive impact of 0.25 with the elasticity on the savings-based model. The inflation rate has a significantly negative on both demands of the life insurance.

In their research titled “Determining the economic and population factors of using life insurance in all countries”, Beck and Webb (2003) studied the relationship between life insurance and a number of economic and population variables for 66 counties using panel data method (with fixed effects) during 1961-2000. Their findings assert the fact that the higher dominance of life insurance leads to higher economic growth. However, in the Muslim communities, this relationship is negative. Beck and Webb showed that when life insurance and banking offers their services complementarily, they have considerably higher impacts on the economic growth compared to when the impact of one of them is estimated on the economic growth. They found a strong relationship between life insurances and the gross domestic products, the dependency burden of the elderly, inflation, banking sector development, and the real interest rate and claimed that the countries with developed banking system, high income, old population, and lower inflation have higher usage of the life insurance and believe that in case the inflation is controlled, a positive relationship exists between the real interest rate and the demand for life insurance. Beck and Webb also showed that the variables of life expectancy, the dependency burden of the youth, and education level do not have a significant impact on purchasing life insurance.

Ebrahim Mokri Gharavern (2008) examined the long-term relationship between the demand for life insurance and the effective factors on it using time series data in Iran during 1979-2007 based on Johansen-Juselius cointegration test. The findings of the research shows that a long-term equilibrium relationship exists between the demand for life insurance and the factors effective on it such that the results show that in long-term, the per capita gross domestic product has a positive and significant impact on the demand for life insurance in Iran and given the fact that the obtained coefficient is larger than 1 (1.45%), one could conclude that in long-term, the demand for life insurance in Iran will be elastic with respect to the income. Also, the insurance demand elasticity with respect to the expectancy variable was -5.02 while not being significant. Furthermore, in long-term, the literacy rate and the expected inflation have positive and significant, and negative and significant relationships with the purchase of life insurance, respectively.

Sajadi et al. (2007) used OLS method to examine the relationship between the macro economic variables and the demand for life insurance in Iran. The most basic findings of this study shows that the gross domestic product as well as the estimated inflation have an effective relationship with the demand for life insurance. The interesting result was the positive relationship of the demand with the insurance price which seems contradictory. Moreover, the life expectancy is evaluated to be quite effective on the demand with a positive coefficient.

Amir Gholami (2006) has used times series data in the period of 1990-2004 to estimate the life insurance demand function using the ordinary least square (OLS) method. The most basic findings of this research show that the gross domestic product as well as the estimated inflation rate have an effective relationship with the demand for life insurance. The interesting result was the positive relationship between the demand for life insurance and the insurance price. Moreover, the life expectancy is evaluated to be quite effective on the demand with a positive coefficient.

Pajooyan and Pourpatoyi (2003) used the statistical data of 1967-2001 to estimate the pattern for the insurance demand and assessed its value by the end of 2004. Their objective was to examine the impact of income, expected inflation, dependency burden, and education level on the demand for the life insurances

in Iran.

3. Methodology

3-1- Estimating the inflation rate, gross domestic product, and interest rate fluctuations

3-1-1- Estimating the inflation rate fluctuations

Before assessing the best model for the inflation rate fluctuations, first, the descriptive statistics of this variable are introduced. The results are presented in the below table.

Table 1: The descriptive statistics for inflation rate

Date: 09/01/17

Time: 22:39

Sample: 1 45

INFLATION	
Mean	18.24889
Median	16.60000
Maximum	49.40000
Minimum	5.500000
Std. Dev.	8.714789
Skewness	-0277987
Kurtosis	2.216219
Jarque-Bera	1.538809
Probability	0.463090
Sum	821.2000
Sum Sq. Dev.	3341.692
Observations	45

Based on the abovementioned results, the inflation rate in the studied time period has the following statistical specifications and based on JB statistic, this variable is normal. The proper selection of q and p has a significant impact on the validity of the obtained results from GARCH pattern. In fact, the estimation of the conditional variance consists of the following three stages:

Selecting the best ARMA pattern for the averaging equation which is usually carried out using Box–Jenkins method. This method is a scientific method which consists of three stages of identification, estimation, and checking. This method mainly uses behavior of the autocorrelation and partial

autocorrelation coefficients.

First stage: Identification

Identification of ARMA models is defined as determining the order of the model. σ^2 is the variance of the residuals which is equal to the summation of the squared errors divided by the degree of freedom, i.e. $n-k$ where $k=p+q+1$. Each of these information criteria are minimized with respect to $p \leq \bar{p}$ and $q \leq \bar{q}$ where \bar{p} and \bar{q} are the higher bounds for the number of MA and AR terms, respectively. Based on the information criteria, the order of ARMA model will be as the following:

$$p = 1, q = 1$$

Second stage: Estimation

The results of the estimation of ARMA process using OLS method are as the following table:

Table 2: Estimation of ARMA process using OLS method

Dependent Variable: INFLATION

Method: ARMA Maximum Likelihood (OPG - BHHH)

Date: 09/01/17 Time: 23:18

Sample: 1 45

Included observations: 45

Convergence achieved after 21 iterations

Coefficient covariance computed using outer product of gradients

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	18.09591	2.153865	8.401597	0.0000
AR(1)	0.093366	0.220108	0.424183	0.6736
MA(1)	0.610607	0.236042	2.586862	0.0133
SIGMASQ	49.26138	11.00376	4.476777	0.0001
R-squared	0.336635	Mean dependent var		18.24889
Adjusted R-squared	0.288096	S.D. dependent var		8.714789
S.E. of regression	7.353052	Akaike info criterion		6.925822
Sum squared resid	2216.762	Schwarz criterion		7.086414
Log likelihood	-151.8310	Hannan-Quinn criter.		6.985689

F-statistic	6.935362	Durbin-Watson stat	1.951620
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000699		

Inverted AR Roots	.09
Inverted MA Roots	-.61

Given the results, the optimal ARMA process based on information criteria is ARMA(1,1).

Third stage: Checking

This stage requires control and rechecking the model, i.e. it is determined whether the model is sufficient. The autocorrelation coefficients for the residuals were calculated for 20 intervals and the results implied that no out-of-bound (dots) coefficients existed. Therefore, no autocorrelation coefficient has a significant difference with zero. Also, Q statistic (Ljung-Box criterion) is small and smaller than the values of χ^2 table. Therefore, the autocorrelation coefficients are not significantly different than zero. The probability values in the last column are larger than 0.05 which indicates the autocorrelation coefficients to be zero. As a result, ARMA(1,1) model is sufficient.

Table 3: The results of the calculation of autocorrelation coefficients of the residuals

Date: 09/01/17

Time: 23:19

Sample: 1 45

Included observations: 45

Q-statistic probabilities adjusted for 2 ARMA terms

Autocorrelation	Partial Correlation		AC	PAC	Q-Stat	Prob
. .	. .	1	-0.000	-0.000	5.E-06	
. .	. .	2	-0.055	-0.055	0.1487	
. .	. .	3	-0.058	-0.058	0.3177	0.573
. *	. .	4	0.075	0.073	0.6102	0.737
. .	. .	5	-0.028	-0.034	0.6510	0.885
. .	. .	6	-0.007	-0.002	0.6537	0.957
. *	. *	7	0.118	0.125	1.4348	0.920
.* .	.* .	8	-0.119	-0.133	2.2392	0.896
. .	. *	9	0.065	0.089	2.4897	0.928
** .	** .	10	-0.276	-0.292	7.0815	0.528

. .	. .	11	0.024	0.023	7.1172	0.625
.* .	.* .	12	-0.099	-0.121	7.7445	0.654
. *	. .	13	0.086	0.060	8.2340	0.692
. .	. .	14	-0.037	-0.030	8.3290	0.759
. .	. .	15	-0.041	-0.029	8.4475	0.813
.* .	.* .	16	-0.078	-0.106	8.8959	0.838
. .	. .	17	-0.049	0.023	9.0745	0.874
. **	. **	18	0.286	0.224	15.495	0.489
.* .	. .	19	-0.072	-0.042	15.912	0.530
.* .	.* .	20	-0.083	-0.172	16.495	0.558

The final stage for the estimation of the inflation rate instability index is estimating the conditional variance equation for the perturbation term under heteroscedastic conditions. Considering the existing ARCH impact as well as using AIC, SBIC, and HQC criteria and based on ARMA(1,1) model and carried out estimations, the hypothesis of heteroscedasticity is approved and the best model capable of showing this heteroscedasticity is obtained to be EGARCH(1,1) model.

This model is another method for the formulation of conditional variance which is as follows:

$$\log(\sigma_t^2) = \omega + \beta \log(\sigma_{t-1}^2) + \gamma \frac{u_{t-1}}{\sqrt{\sigma_{t-1}^2}} + \alpha \left[\frac{|u_{t-1}|}{\sqrt{\sigma_{t-1}^2}} - \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \right] \quad (1)$$

The results of the estimated model are as follow for EGARCH model:

Table 4: The results of the estimated model for EGARCH model

Heteroskedasticity Test: ARCH

F-statistic	1.755754	Prob. F(1,42)	0.3210
Obs*R-squared	1.303093	Prob. Chi-Square(1)	0.3213

Dependent Variable: INFLATION

Method: ML ARCH - Normal distribution (OPG - BHHH / Marquardt steps)

Date: 09/01/17 Time: 23:36

Sample: 1 45

Included observations: 45

Convergence not achieved after 500 iterations

Coefficient covariance computed using outer product of gradients

Presample variance: backcast (parameter = 0.7)

$$\text{LOG(GARCH)} = C(4) + C(5)*\text{ABS}(\text{RESID}(-1)/\text{SQRT}(\text{GARCH}(-1))) + C(6) \\ * \text{RESID}(-1)/\text{SQRT}(\text{GARCH}(-1)) + C(7)*\text{LOG}(\text{GARCH}(-1))$$

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
C	16.88165	1.536623	10.98621	0.0000
AR(1)	0.009575	0.267562	0.035788	0.9715
MA(1)	0.556420	0.180939	3.075177	0.0021

Variance Equation

C(4)	2.400700	2.175560	1.103486	0.2698
C(5)	0.711276	0.631948	1.125528	0.2604
C(6)	0.419042	0.301599	1.389403	0.1647
C(7)	0.173112	0.576309	0.300380	0.7639

R-squared	0.312250	Mean dependent var	18.24889
Adjusted R-squared	0.279500	S.D. dependent var	8.714789
S.E. of regression	7.397313	Akaike info criterion	6.823393
Sum squared resid	2298.250	Schwarz criterion	7.104429
Log likelihood	-146.5263	Hannan-Quinn criter.	6.928161
Durbin-Watson stat	1.671950		

Inverted AR Roots .01

Inverted MA Roots -.56

Heteroskedasticity Test: ARCH

F-statistic	0.064021	Prob. F(1,42)	0.8015
Obs*R-squared	0.066968	Prob. Chi-Square(1)	0.7958

$$\log(\sigma_t^2) = 2.4007 + 0.7112 \log(\sigma_{t-1}^2) + 0.4190 \frac{u_{t-1}}{\sqrt{\sigma_{t-1}^2}} + 0.1731 \left[\frac{|u_{t-1}|}{\sqrt{\sigma_{t-1}^2}} - \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \right] \tag{2}$$

(1.1034) (1.1255) (1.3894) (0.3003)

The test results show that the perturbation terms are normally distributed and therefore, EGARCH(1,1) model is correctly expressed. Also, since statistic t is significant for γ (1.3894) which indicates that the shocks applied to the inflation rate are asymmetric and since coefficient γ is positive, the impact of the negative shocks are higher than that of the positive shocks.

The impact of negative shocks: $0.419042 + 0.173112 = 0.592154$

The impact of negative shocks: $\gamma + \alpha = 0.592154$

The impact of positive shocks: $\gamma = 0.419042$

As a result, by using EGARCH or exponential GARCH method, the inflation rate index is estimated. The results of the inflation rate fluctuations are illustrated in the following diagram based on the estimated model.

Figure 1. Inflation rate fluctuations

Figure 2. Inflation rate fluctuations

3-1-2- Estimating the gross domestic product fluctuations

In this study, the gross domestic product is assumed to be formed in an autoregressive process of order p as the following equation:

$$GDP_t = \lambda_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \lambda_i GDP_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \tag{3}$$

Where GDP_t is the gross domestic product based on the base price of 2004 and ε_t is formed the based on the available information at time t (ψ_(t-1)) with a normal distribution with zero mean and variance h_t. Before estimating the best model for the gross domestic product fluctuations index, the descriptive statistics of this variable is first introduced. The results are illustrated in the below table.

Table 5: The descriptive statistics of the inflation rate fluctuations

Date: 10/21/17

Time: 14:04

Sample: 1 45

GDP	
Mean	1479718.
Median	106210.4

Maximum	9654234.
Minimum	981.2000
Std. Dev.	2587661.
Skewness	1.867870
Kurtosis	0.310924
Jarque-Bera	0.818023
Probability	0.365789
Sum	66587296
Sum Sq. Dev.	2.95E+14
Observations	45

Based on the abovementioned results, the variable of gross domestic product has had the specified statistical specifications in the studied period and based on JB statistic, it is a normal variable. In what follows, the gross domestic product index is estimated. The proper selection of q and p has a significant impact on the validity of the obtained results from GARCH pattern. In fact, the estimation of the conditional variance consists of the following three stages:

First stage: Identification

Identification of ARMA models is defined as determining the order of the model. The objective is to select the model such that the value of the information criterion is minimized. Different criteria are introduced which include Akaike information criterion (AIC), Bayesian - Schwarz information criterion (SBIC), and Hannan–Quinn information criterion. Based on the information criteria, the order of ARMA model will be as the following:

$$p = 1, q = 1$$

Second stage: Estimation

The results of the estimation of ARMA process using OLS method are as the following table. The numbers inside parentheses indicate the t statistic.

Table 6: The results of estimation of ARMA process using OLS method

Dependent Variable: GDP

Method: ARMA Maximum Likelihood (OPG - BHHH)

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Date: 09/01/17 Time: 23:50

Sample: 1 45

Included observations: 45

Convergence achieved after 48 iterations

Coefficient covariance computed using outer product of gradients

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	4875059.	5735434.	0.849990	0.4003
AR(1)	0.994098	0.055124	18.03377	0.0000
MA(1)	0.721146	0.116342	6.198513	0.0000
SIGMASQ	1.05E+11	1.44E+10	7.266174	0.0000
R-squared	0.983990	Mean dependent var		1479718.
Adjusted R-squared	0.982818	S.D. dependent var		2587661.
S.E. of regression	339189.3	Akaike info criterion		28.53024
Sum squared resid	4.72E+12	Schwarz criterion		28.69084
Log likelihood	-637.9305	Hannan-Quinn criter.		28.59011
F-statistic	839.9482	Durbin-Watson stat		1.023073
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Given the results of the table above, the results of the estimation of ARMA process are as follows:

$$P = 1.50 + 0.1639P(-1) + 0.2066MA(1) \quad (4)$$

The above equation shows that the optimal ARMA process based on information criteria is ARMA(1,1).

Third stage: Checking

This stage requires control and rechecking the model, i.e. it is determined whether the model is sufficient. The autocorrelation coefficients for the residuals were calculated for 20 intervals and the results implied that no out-of-bound (dots) coefficients existed. Therefore, no autocorrelation coefficient has a significant difference with zero. The probability values in the last column are larger than 0.05 which indicates the autocorrelation coefficients to be zero. As a result, ARMA(1,1) model is sufficient.

Table 7: The results of calculating the autocorrelation coefficients for the residuals for 20 intervals

Date: 09/01/17 Time: 23:58

Sample: 1 45

Included observations: 44

Q-statistic probabilities adjusted for 2 ARMA terms

Autocorrelation	Partial Correlation	AC	PAC	Q-Stat	Prob
. .	. .	1	-0.015	-0.015	0.0108
** .	** .	2	-0.206	-0.206	2.0512
* .	* .	3	-0.083	-0.094	2.3926 0.122
. **	. **	4	0.338	0.306	8.1609 0.017
. **	. **	5	0.290	0.312	12.524 0.006
. .	. *	6	-0.048	0.113	12.645 0.013
. .	. *	7	-0.029	0.150	12.693 0.026
. *	. *	8	0.140	0.131	13.799 0.032
. .	* .	9	0.036	-0.142	13.876 0.053
. .	* .	10	0.002	-0.117	13.876 0.085
. .	. .	11	0.063	-0.013	14.121 0.118
. .	* .	12	-0.006	-0.173	14.123 0.167
. .	. .	13	0.017	-0.057	14.142 0.225
. .	. .	14	-0.037	-0.011	14.234 0.286
. .	. .	15	0.003	-0.044	14.235 0.358
. .	. .	16	0.012	0.001	14.245 0.432
. .	. .	17	-0.020	0.051	14.276 0.505
. .	. .	18	-0.029	0.007	14.340 0.573
. .	. .	19	-0.026	-0.004	14.394 0.639
. .	. .	20	-0.021	0.020	14.432 0.701

The results of the stability test of the perturbation term is presented in the table below. Based on the results of this table, one could state for the perturbation term that the value of ADF and modified Dickey-Fuller tests statistic is higher than the critical value and the zero assumption is rejected based on the instability of the perturbation term.

The final stage for the estimation of the inflation rate instability index, is estimating the conditional
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variance equation of the perturbation term under heteroscedastic conditions.

Considering the existing ARCH impact as well as using AIC, SBIC, and HQC criteria and based on ARMA(1,1) model and carried out estimations, the hypothesis of heteroscedasticity is approved and the best model capable of showing this heteroscedasticity is obtained to be EGARCH(1,1) model. The results of the estimated model for EGARCH model are as follows:

Table 8: The results of the estimated model for EGARCH model

Heteroskedasticity Test: ARCH

F-statistic	1.755754	Prob. F(1,42)	0.3210
Obs*R-squared	1.303093	Prob. Chi-Square(1)	0.3213

Dependent Variable: DGDP

Method: ML ARCH - Normal distribution (OPG - BHHH / Marquardt steps)

Date: 09/01/17 Time: 23:56

Sample (adjusted): 2 45

Included observations: 44 after adjustments

Failure to improve likelihood (non-zero gradients) after 66 iterations

Coefficient covariance computed using outer product of gradients

Presample variance: backcast (parameter = 0.7)

LOG(GARCH) = C(4) + C(5)*ABS(RESID(-1)/@SQRT(GARCH(-1))) + C(6)
*RESID(-1)/@SQRT(GARCH(-1)) + C(7)*LOG(GARCH(-1))

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
C	142518.3	11268.33	12.64769	0.0000
AR(1)	0.526675	0.036659	14.36674	0.0000
MA(1)	-0.283991	0.003315	-85.68093	0.0000

Variance Equation

C(4)	25.23222	0.007946	3175.322	0.0000
C(5)	-0.871599	0.013308	-65.49627	0.0000
C(6)	1.593522	0.038574	41.31123	0.0000
C(7)	0.001679	0.000313	5.367593	0.0000

R-squared	0.325862	Mean dependent var	219392.1
Adjusted R-squared	0.292977	S.D. dependent var	365867.3
S.E. of regression	307638.3	Akaike info criterion	27.39813
Sum squared resid	3.88E+12	Schwarz criterion	27.68198
Log likelihood	-595.7589	Hannan-Quinn criter.	27.50340
Durbin-Watson stat	0.853922		
<hr/>			
Inverted AR Roots		.53	
Inverted MA Roots		.28	

$$\log(\sigma_t^2) = 25.2322 - 0.8715 \log(\sigma_{t-1}^2) + 1.5935 \frac{u_{t-1}}{\sqrt{\sigma_{t-1}^2}} + 0.0016 \left[\frac{|u_{t-1}|}{\sqrt{\sigma_{t-1}^2}} - \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \right] \quad (5)$$

(3175.322) (-65.4962) (41.3112) (5.3675)

The test results show that the perturbation terms are normally distributed and therefore, EGARCH(1,1) model is correctly expressed. Also, since statistic t is significant for γ (41.3112) which indicates that the shocks applied to the inflation rate are asymmetric and since coefficient γ is positive, the impact of the negative shocks are higher than that of the positive shocks.

The impact of negative shocks: $1.593522 + 0.001679 = 1.595201$

The impact of negative shocks: $\gamma + \alpha = 1.5952$

The impact of positive shocks: $\gamma = 1.5935$

According to the following diagram, the estimated model was tested in terms of the perturbation term and the perturbation terms of the estimated model is normal.

Figure 3. Terms of the perturbation term and the perturbation terms of the model

As a result, by using EGARCH or exponential GARCH method, the gross domestic product index is estimated. The results of the gross domestic product fluctuations are illustrated in the following diagram based on the estimated model.

Figure 4. The gross domestic product fluctuations

3-1-3- Estimating the interest rate fluctuations

In this study, the interest rate fluctuations are estimated in the form of GARCH model.

Before estimating the best model for the interest rate fluctuations index, the descriptive statistic of this variable is first introduced. The results are illustrated in below table.

Table 9: The descriptive statistic for the interest rate fluctuations

Date: 10/21/17

Time: 14:17

Sample: 1 45

INTEREST	
Mean	7.504444
Median	7.000000
Maximum	12.000000
Minimum	6.000000
Std. Dev.	1.190293
Skewness	1.318839
Kurtosis	0.926905
Jarque-Bera	1.104773
Probability	0.325678
Sum	337.7000
Sum Sq. Dev.	62.33911
Observations	45

Based on the abovementioned results, the variable of interest rate has had the specified statistical specifications in the studied period and based on JB statistic, it is a normal variable. The proper selection of q and p has a significant impact on the validity of the obtained results from GARCH pattern. In fact, the estimation of the conditional variance consists of the following three stages:

First stage: Identification

Identification of ARMA models is defined as determining the order of the model. $\hat{\sigma}^2$ is the variance of the residuals which is equal to the summation of the squared errors divided by the degree of freedom, i.e. $n-k$ where $k=p+q+1$. Each of these information criteria are minimized with respect to $p \leq \bar{p}$ and $q \leq \bar{q}$ where \bar{p} and \bar{q} are the higher bounds for the number of MA and AR terms, respectively. Based on the information criteria, the order of ARMA model will be as the following:

$$p = 1, q = 1$$

Second stage: Estimation

The results of the estimation of ARMA process using OLS method are as the following table. The numbers inside parentheses indicate the t statistic.

Table 10: The results of estimation of ARMA process using OLS method

Dependent Variable: INTEREST

Method: ARMA Maximum Likelihood (OPG - BHHH)

Date: 09/02/17 Time: 00:23

Sample: 1 45

Included observations: 45

Convergence achieved after 33 iterations

Coefficient covariance computed using outer product of gradients

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	7.727085	0.615925	12.54549	0.0000
AR(1)	0.658849	0.135586	4.859275	0.0000
MA(1)	0.414436	0.240545	1.722903	0.0924
SIGMASQ	0.632108	0.106125	5.956285	0.0000
R-squared	0.543708	Mean dependent var		7.504444
Adjusted R-squared	0.510321	S.D. dependent var		1.190293
S.E. of regression	0.832933	Akaike info criterion		2.584528
Sum squared resid	28.44485	Schwarz criterion		2.745120
Log likelihood	-54.15188	Hannan-Quinn criter.		2.644395
F-statistic	16.28490	Durbin-Watson stat		1.688916
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			
Inverted AR Roots			.66	
Inverted MA Roots			-.41	

Considering the results, the optimal ARMA process based on information criteria is ARMA(1,1).

Third stage: Checking

This stage requires control and rechecking the model, i.e. it is determined whether the model is sufficient. The autocorrelation coefficients for the residuals were calculated for 20 intervals and the results implied that no out-of-bound (dots) coefficients existed. Therefore, no autocorrelation coefficient has a significant difference with zero. Also, Q statistic (Ljung-Box criterion) is small and smaller than the values of χ^2 table. Therefore, the autocorrelation coefficients are not significantly different than zero. The probability values in the last column are larger than 0.05 which indicates the autocorrelation coefficients to be zero. As a result, ARMA(1,1) model is sufficient.

Table 11: The results of the calculation of autocorrelation coefficients of the residuals for 20 intervals

Date: 09/02/17 Time: 00:24

Sample: 1 45

Included observations: 45

Q-statistic probabilities adjusted for 2 ARMA terms

Autocorrelation	Partial Correlation		AC	PAC	Q-Stat	Prob
. .	. .	1	0.046	0.046	0.1028	
. .	. .	2	0.021	0.019	0.1249	
. .	. .	3	-0.053	-0.055	0.2679	0.605
. .	. .	4	0.041	0.046	0.3562	0.837
* .	* .	5	-0.148	-0.151	1.5083	0.680
. .	* .	6	0.066	0.079	1.7452	0.782
* .	* .	7	0.085	0.089	2.1449	0.829
. .	* .	8	-0.052	-0.087	2.2983	0.890
. .	. .	9	0.026	0.057	2.3392	0.939
. .	* .	10	-0.044	-0.070	2.4548	0.964
. .	. .	11	-0.062	-0.054	2.6913	0.975
* .	. .	12	-0.091	-0.048	3.2180	0.976
. .	* .	13	-0.039	-0.078	3.3174	0.986
* .	. .	14	-0.080	-0.059	3.7511	0.988
. .	. .	15	0.033	0.034	3.8291	0.993
* .	* .	16	0.110	0.094	4.7066	0.989
. .	. .	17	-0.019	-0.036	4.7340	0.994
. .	. .	18	-0.024	-0.018	4.7777	0.997
. .	* .	19	0.065	0.078	5.1235	0.997

. .		. .		20	0.022	0.019	5.1649	0.999
-------	--	-------	--	----	-------	-------	--------	-------

The final stage for the estimation of the interest rate instability index is estimating the conditional variance equation for the perturbation term under heteroscedastic conditions. Considering the existing ARCH impact as well as using AIC, SBIC, and HQC criteria and based on ARMA(1,1) model and carried out estimations, the hypothesis of heteroscedasticity is approved and the best model capable of showing this heteroscedasticity is obtained to be EGARCH(1,1) model. EGARCH(1,1) or exponential GARCH models was proposed by Nelson (1991).

This model is another method for the formulation of conditional variance which is as follows:

$$\log(\sigma_t^2) = \omega + \beta \log(\sigma_{t-1}^2) + \gamma \frac{u_{t-1}}{\sqrt{\sigma_{t-1}^2}} + \alpha \left[\frac{|u_{t-1}|}{\sqrt{\sigma_{t-1}^2}} - \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \right] \tag{6}$$

The results of the estimated model for EGARCH model are as follows:

Table 12: The results of the estimated model for EGARCH model

Heteroskedasticity Test: ARCH

F-statistic	1.655754	Prob. F(1,42)	0.3564
Obs*R-squared	1.203093	Prob. Chi-Square(1)	0.3478

Dependent Variable: INTEREST

Method: ML ARCH - Normal distribution (OPG - BHHH / Marquardt steps)

Date: 09/02/17 Time: 00:25

Sample: 1 45

Included observations: 45

Failure to improve likelihood (non-zero gradients) after 367 iterations

Coefficient covariance computed using outer product of gradients

Presample variance: backcast (parameter = 0.7)

LOG(GARCH) = C(4) + C(5)*ABS(RESID(-1)/@SQRT(GARCH(-1))) + C(6)
 *RESID(-1)/@SQRT(GARCH(-1)) + C(7)*LOG(GARCH(-1))

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
C	7.927914	0.386046	20.53617	0.0000

AR(1)	0.942647	0.015797	59.67206	0.0000
MA(1)	0.037634	0.019237	1.956373	0.0504
Variance Equation				
C(4)	-0.167253	0.212297	-0.787825	0.4308
C(5)	-1.916387	0.366075	-5.234959	0.0000
C(6)	1.990284	0.302462	6.580279	0.0000
C(7)	0.044638	0.162736	0.274298	0.7839
R-squared	0.489961	Mean dependent var	7.504444	
Adjusted R-squared	0.465673	S.D. dependent var	1.190293	
S.E. of regression	0.870077	Akaike info criterion	1.872499	
Sum squared resid	31.79540	Schwarz criterion	2.153535	
Log likelihood	-35.13123	Hannan-Quinn criter.	1.977266	
Durbin-Watson stat	1.507226			
Inverted AR Roots			.94	
Inverted MA Roots			-.04	

$$\log(\sigma_t^2) = -0.1672 - 1.9162 \log(\sigma_{t-1}^2) + 1.9902 \frac{u_{t-1}}{\sqrt{\sigma_{t-1}^2}} + 0.0446 \left[\frac{|u_{t-1}|}{\sqrt{\sigma_{t-1}^2}} - \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \right] \tag{7}$$

(-0.7878) (-5.2349) (6.5802) (0.2742)

The test results show that the perturbation terms are normally distributed and therefore, EGARCH(1,1) model is correctly expressed. Also, since statistic t is significant for γ (6.5802) which indicates that the shocks applied to the inflation rate are asymmetric and since coefficient γ is positive, the impact of the negative shocks are higher than that of the positive shocks.

The impact of negative shocks: $1.990284 + 0.044638 = 2.034922$

The impact of negative shocks: $\gamma + \alpha = 2.03492$

The impact of positive shocks: $\gamma = 1.99028$

As a result, by using EGARCH or exponential GARCH method, the interest rate index is estimated. The results of the interest rate fluctuations are illustrated in the following diagram based on the estimated model.

Figure 5. The interest rate fluctuations

Figure 6. The interest rate fluctuations

3-2- The descriptive statistics of the research variables and pattern estimation

3-2-1) The fluctuation of inflation rate, gross domestic product, and interest rate and life insurance premiums

Table 13: The fluctuation of inflation rate, gross domestic product, and interest rate and life insurance premiums

Date: 09/02/17

Time: 00:40

Sample: 1 45

	RESIDUALGDP	RESIDUALINFLATION	RESIDUALINTEREST	RESIDUALPREMIUM
Mean	51285.94	0.629466	-0.000985	1542.389
Median	-81952.90	0.111640	-0.012450	15.20000
Maximum	1177303.	23.38670	1.948710	22597.50
Minimum	-151920.0	-10.39230	-2.938070	0.200000
Std. Dev.	296987.9	7.308515	0.813546	4261.769
Skewness	0.547046	0.801963	-0.820445	0.839780
Kurtosis	2.275136	3.833035	1.216222	2.713523
Jarque-Bera	1.356222	4.580312	1.936795	3.016752
Probability	0.643578	0.121412	0.456783	0.236845
Sum	2102723.	25.80809	-0.040370	63237.94
Sum Sq. Dev.	3.53E+12	2136.575	26.47430	7.27E+08
Observations	41	41	41	41

Variance-covariance matrix (autocorrelation coefficients)

Table 14: Variance-covariance matrix (autocorrelation coefficients)

Covariance Analysis: Ordinary

Date: 09/24/17 Time: 19:18

Page | 23

Sample: 1 44

Included observations: 41

Balanced sample (listwise missing value deletion)

Probability	Correlation			RESIDUALINT EREST
	PREMIUM	RESIDUALINFL ATION	RESIDUALGDP	
PREMIUM	1.000000 ----- -----			
RESIDUALINFLATIO N	-0.033127 -3.206989 0.000341	1.000000 ----- -----		
RESIDUALGDP	0.622936 4.972985 0.000000	-0.185419 -1.178375 0.2458	1.000000 ----- -----	
ESIDUALINTEREST	0.289521 2.888957 0.003464	0.167439 1.060629 0.2954	-0.292444 -1.909802 0.0635	1.000000 ----- -----

3-2-2- Estimating the vector autoregression (VAR) pattern

In the vector autoregression pattern (VAR), it is required to initially determine the optimal interval length and then carry out the estimation step which is described as follows.

Table 15: Estimating the vector autoregression (VAR) patter

VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria

Endogenous variables: PREMIUM RESIDUALINFLATION RESIDUALGDP
RESIDUALINTEREST

Exogenous variables: C

Date: 09/02/17 Time: 00:44

Sample: 1 45

Included observations: 33

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-865.8048	NA	9.21e+17	52.71544	52.89684	52.77647
1	-769.9681	162.6320	7.36e+15	47.87685	48.78383	48.18202
2	-733.3467	53.26737*	2.21e+15*	46.62708*	48.25963*	47.17638*

* indicates lag order selected by the criterion

LR: sequential modified LR test statistic (each test at 5% level)

FPE: Final prediction error

AIC: Akaike information criterion

SC: Schwarz information criterion

HQ: Hannan-Quinn information criterion

Vector Autoregression Estimates

Date: 09/02/17 Time: 00:42

Sample (adjusted): 3 41

Included observations: 33 after adjustments

Standard errors in () & t-statistics in []

	PREMIUM	RESIDUALINF LATION	RESIDUALGD P	RESIDUALINT EREST
PREMIUM(-1)	1.769622 (0.22229) [7.96078]	-0.006887 (0.00869) [-0.79251]	254.2539 (130.129) [1.95386]	-0.001621 (0.00096) [-1.68788]

PREMIUM(-2)	-0.157273 (0.30346) [-0.51826]	0.008676 (0.01186) [0.73133]	319.2576 (177.645) [1.79716]	0.001165 (0.00131) [0.88877]
RESIDUALINFLATION(-1)	4.949088 (3.92251) [1.26171]	-0.208852 (0.15334) [-1.36204]	-489.3879 (2296.22) [-0.21313]	0.023700 (0.01695) [1.39824]
RESIDUALINFLATION(-2)	0.119584 (3.55388) [0.03365]	0.013939 (0.13893) [0.10033]	1500.188 (2080.43) [0.72110]	-0.021127 (0.01536) [-1.37574]
RESIDUALGDP(-1)	-0.000637 (0.00028) [-2.24874]	3.29E-06 (1.1E-05) [0.29732]	-0.443393 (0.16575) [-2.67514]	4.96E-07 (1.2E-06) [0.40542]
RESIDUALGDP(-2)	-0.000754 (0.00030) [-2.51263]	-3.48E-06 (1.2E-05) [-0.29648]	-1.386359 (0.17573) [-7.88893]	3.82E-06 (1.3E-06) [2.94854]
RESIDUALINTEREST(-1)	-77.67476 (46.3442) [-1.67604]	-3.414599 (1.81167) [-1.88478]	38380.72 (27129.8) [1.41471]	-0.053318 (0.20026) [-0.26624]
RESIDUALINTEREST(-2)	-0.927081 (50.4468) [-0.01838]	-1.656341 (1.97205) [-0.83991]	-15178.37 (29531.4) [-0.51397]	-0.025637 (0.21799) [-0.11761]
C	-145.5276 (48.5914) [-2.99493]	-0.052503 (1.89952) [-0.02764]	-233400.2 (28445.2) [-8.20525]	0.333408 (0.20997) [1.58790]
R-squared	0.993893	0.296960	0.930317	0.605298
Adj. R-squared	0.991857	0.062613	0.907089	0.473730

Sum sq. resids	455545.4	696.1443	1.56E+11	8.505904
S.E. equation	137.7718	5.385723	80651.14	0.595326
F-statistic	488.2460	1.267181	40.05214	4.600665
Log likelihood	-204.1152	-97.13429	-414.4008	-24.45514
Akaike AIC	12.91607	6.432381	25.66065	2.027585
Schwarz SC	13.32421	6.840519	26.06879	2.435723
Mean dependent	688.1261	0.171632	21389.92	-0.075275
S.D. dependent	1526.791	5.562686	264592.7	0.820636
Determinant resid covariance (dof adj.)		8.43E+14		
Determinant resid covariance		2.36E+14		
Log likelihood		-733.3467		
Akaike information criterion		46.62708		
Schwarz criterion		48.25963		

3-3- Variance analysis functions and instantaneous response functions and results analysis:

As expressed before, since the interpretation of the individual coefficients in the estimated VAR models are often difficult, instantaneous response and variance analysis functions are practically estimated. In this regard, these diagrams are estimated and analyzed in what follows:

3-3-1- The impact of a positive shock (one standard deviation) in the percentage of the economic fluctuations on the life insurance

Table 16: The impact of a positive shock (one standard deviation) in the percentage of the economic fluctuations on the life insurance.

Response of PREMIUM:				
Period	PREMIUM	RESIDUALINF LATION	RESIDUALGD P	RESIDUALINT EREST
1	137.7718 (16.9585)	0.000000 (0.00000)	0.000000 (0.00000)	0.000000 (0.00000)
2	254.7849	22.12022	-34.12842	-42.91197

	(48.1475)	(22.9826)	(20.0168)	(26.1424)
3	437.9743	27.16853	-90.60373	-96.99850
	(97.8443)	(44.3272)	(39.0066)	(59.2495)
4	652.7715	35.95932	-95.38991	-164.7336
	(177.664)	(72.8407)	(56.0187)	(109.810)
5	970.8685	51.01854	-129.1804	-234.6257
	(302.043)	(105.822)	(88.3236)	(177.292)
6	1495.357	98.56400	-263.5706	-350.2157
	(504.936)	(159.810)	(148.048)	(277.573)
7	2242.818	141.1357	-377.0446	-555.1806
	(833.277)	(246.953)	(230.002)	(439.647)
8	3318.340	185.7859	-484.8642	-824.8617
	(1357.50)	(367.701)	(350.563)	(685.503)
9	5005.127	303.2101	-798.4374	-1204.203
	(2201.32)	(545.489)	(552.260)	(1053.27)
10	7549.693	475.6517	-1264.250	-1836.245
	(3562.73)	(827.581)	(872.010)	(1630.41)

Figure 7. The impact of a positive shock (one standard deviation) in the percentage of the economic fluctuations on the life insurance.

3-3-2- Variance analysis

Variance analysis shows the estimation error percentage for the sales of life insurance compared to when a positive shock (one standard deviation) is applied to the economic fluctuations for 10 years. In other words, the shares of each of the aforementioned variables on the changes of the patterns in the sales of life insurance are illustrated.

Table 17: Variance analysis

Variance Decomposition of PREMIUM:

Period	S.E.	PREMIUM	RESIDUALINF	RESIDUALGD	RESIDUALINT
--------	------	---------	-------------	------------	-------------

			LATION	P	EREST
1	137.7718	100.0000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
2	295.6212	96.00021	0.559897	1.332789	2.107104
3	545.4990	92.65671	0.412487	3.150119	3.780683
4	872.4731	92.19915	0.331119	2.426799	5.042936
5	1333.467	92.47973	0.288133	1.977387	5.254749
6	2053.305	92.04101	0.351946	2.481701	5.125340
7	3117.147	91.70633	0.357713	2.539907	5.396053
8	4655.963	91.90022	0.319559	2.222928	5.557295
9	6993.484	91.95357	0.329614	2.288725	5.428090
10	10540.54	91.78080	0.348735	2.446122	5.424341

Figure 8. Variance analysis

As observed, the fluctuation in the sales of life insurance in different time periods are mainly explained by the shocks associated with this variable, such that in short-term, in the first year, 100% of the error variance of the life insurance sales are explained by this variable. However, in the second year, this value is decreased to 96.0002% while in the same period, inflation rate, gross domestic product, and interest rate fluctuation variables account for 0.56%, 1.33%, and 2.1% of the error variance of the pattern dependent variable. Anyway, in the 10th year of life insurance sale, this variable accounts for 91.87% of its variations. Accordingly, the interest rate fluctuations have the highest impact on the sales of life insurance by 5.42%.

3-3-3- Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) pattern

Table 18: Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) pattern

Dependent Variable: PREMIUM

Method: ARDL

Date: 09/02/17 Time: 00:55

Sample (adjusted): 5 41

Included observations: 27 after adjustments

Maximum dependent lags: 4 (Automatic selection)

Model selection method: Akaike info criterion (AIC)

Dynamic regressors (4 lags, automatic): RESIDUALINFLATION

RESIDUALGDP RESIDUALINTEREST

Fixed regressors: C

Number of models evaluated: 500

Selected Model: ARDL(4, 4, 3, 1)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
PREMIUM(-1)	0.435194	0.318102	1.368096	0.1986
PREMIUM(-2)	-3.984071	0.998278	-3.990943	0.0021
PREMIUM(-3)	-0.361847	0.372607	-0.971122	0.3524
PREMIUM(-4)	5.259310	0.600612	8.756581	0.0000
RESIDUALINFLATION	-2.625373	1.167651	-2.248422	0.0460
RESIDUALINFLATION(-1)	-0.598482	1.174731	-0.509463	0.6205
RESIDUALINFLATION(-2)	-1.401120	1.114383	-1.257306	0.2347
RESIDUALINFLATION(-3)	-0.861641	1.003755	-0.858417	0.4090
RESIDUALINFLATION(-4)	-2.547997	0.825130	-3.087996	0.0103
RESIDUALGDP	-0.001763	0.000900	-1.959283	0.0759
RESIDUALGDP(-1)	0.005486	0.000877	6.252032	0.0001
RESIDUALGDP(-2)	0.003273	0.000491	6.661787	0.0000

RESIDUALGDP(-3)	0.005609	0.001684	3.330131	0.0067
RESIDUALINTEREST	3.712241	11.72960	0.316485	0.7576
RESIDUALINTEREST(-1)	-18.74210	13.06701	-1.434306	0.1793
C	1177.277	191.6030	6.144355	0.0001
<hr/>				
R-squared	0.999903	Mean dependent var	684.4541	
Adjusted R-squared	0.999771	S.D. dependent var	1634.826	
S.E. of regression	24.73261	Akaike info criterion	9.541366	
Sum squared resid	6728.721	Schwarz criterion	10.30927	
Log likelihood	-112.8084	Hannan-Quinn criter.	9.769704	
F-statistic	7572.568	Durbin-Watson stat	1.537829	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

*Note: p-values and any subsequent tests do not account for model selection.

Long-run coefficients for ARDL pattern

Table 19: Long-run coefficients for ARDL pattern

ARDL Long Run Form and Bounds Test

Dependent Variable: D(PREMIUM)

Selected Model: ARDL(4, 4, 3, 1)

Case 2: Restricted Constant and No Trend

Date: 09/24/17 Time: 18:20

Sample: 1 45

Included observations: 27

Conditional Error Correction Regression

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
----------	-------------	------------	-------------	-------

C	1177.277	191.6030	6.144355	0.0001
PREMIUM(-1)*	0.348586	0.126025	2.765996	0.0184
RESIDUALINFLATION(-1)	-8.034614	2.996498	-2.681334	0.0214
RESIDUALGDP(-1)	0.012605	0.002042	6.171814	0.0001
RESIDUALINTEREST(-1)	-15.02986	17.48499	-0.859587	0.4084
D(PREMIUM(-1))	-0.913392	0.381172	-2.396273	0.0355
D(PREMIUM(-2))	-4.897463	0.720588	-6.796485	0.0000
D(PREMIUM(-3))	-5.259310	0.600612	-8.756581	0.0000
D(RESIDUALINFLATION)	-2.625373	1.167651	-2.248422	0.0460
D(RESIDUALINFLATION(-1))	4.810759	1.855479	2.592732	0.0250
D(RESIDUALINFLATION(-2))	3.409638	1.257935	2.710504	0.0203
D(RESIDUALINFLATION(-3))	2.547997	0.825130	3.087996	0.0103
D(RESIDUALGDP)	-0.001763	0.000900	-1.959283	0.0759
D(RESIDUALGDP(-1))	-0.008883	0.001884	-4.713856	0.0006
D(RESIDUALGDP(-2))	-0.005609	0.001684	-3.330131	0.0067
D(RESIDUALINTEREST)	3.712241	11.72960	0.316485	0.7576

* p-value incompatible with t-Bounds distribution.

Levels Equation

Case 2: Restricted Constant and No Trend

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
RESIDUALINFLATION	23.04916	14.24142	1.618460	0.1339
RESIDUALGDP	-0.036160	0.018259	-1.980420	0.0732
RESIDUALINTEREST	43.11665	53.44514	0.806746	0.4369
C	-3377.293	1705.445	-1.980301	0.0732

$$EC = \text{PREMIUM} - (23.0492 * \text{RESIDUALINFLATION} - 0.0362 * \text{RESIDUALGDP} +$$

43.1167*RESIDUALINTEREST -3377.2929)

ARDL Error correction regression pattern

Table 20: ARDL Error correction regression pattern

ARDL Error Correction Regression

Dependent Variable: D(PREMIUM)

Selected Model: ARDL(4, 4, 3, 1)

Case 2: Restricted Constant and No Trend

Date: 09/24/17 Time: 18:23

Sample: 1 45

Included observations: 27

ECM Regression				
Case 2: Restricted Constant and No Trend				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(PREMIUM(-1))	-0.913392	0.212493	-4.298463	0.0013
D(PREMIUM(-2))	-4.897463	0.342448	-14.30134	0.0000
D(PREMIUM(-3))	-5.259310	0.292574	-17.97598	0.0000
D(RESIDUALINFLATION)	-2.625373	0.719030	-3.651269	0.0038
D(RESIDUALINFLATION(-1))	4.810759	0.845983	5.686589	0.0001
D(RESIDUALINFLATION(-2))	3.409638	0.630981	5.403708	0.0002
D(RESIDUALINFLATION(-3))	2.547997	0.607810	4.192098	0.0015
D(RESIDUALGDP)	-0.001763	0.000507	-3.478275	0.0052
D(RESIDUALGDP(-1))	-0.008883	0.000671	-13.24223	0.0000
D(RESIDUALGDP(-2))	-0.005609	0.000755	-7.431365	0.0000
D(RESIDUALINTEREST)	3.712241	6.957229	0.533580	0.6042
CointEq(-1)*	-0.348586	0.017528	-19.88749	0.0000

R-squared	0.999063	Mean dependent var	209.9059
Adjusted R-squared	0.998376	S.D. dependent var	525.6170
S.E. of regression	21.17974	Akaike info criterion	9.245069
Sum squared resid	6728.721	Schwarz criterion	9.820997
Log likelihood	-112.8084	Hannan-Quinn criter.	9.416323
Durbin-Watson stat	1.537829		

* p-value incompatible with t-Bounds distribution.

4- Conclusion

The results of this research are as follows:

1. According to the regression model, among the factors of the regression pattern and the various regression equations tests, three factors called gross domestic product (GDP), inflation rate, and interest rate are considered as the economic risks and effective factors on the sales of life insurances.
2. Considering the theoretical principles, the relationships among the effective variables and the dependent variable are entirely obtained in theoretical frameworks such that the relationships among the gross domestic product, inflation rate, interest rate, and the index for the total sales of life insurances are evaluated to be in line with theoretical principles.
3. Considering the results associated with the short-term and long-term relationships expressed in the fourth section, the following conclusions are made:
 - a) The gross domestic product is obtained to be 2.44 using regression techniques, i.e. 1% increase in the GDP leads to 2.44% increase in the total sales index of the life insurances and this indicates the direct relationship between these two variables.
 - b) Another effective factor on the total sales index of the life insurances is the inflation rate which is considered as one of the economic risks for which the coefficient is obtained through regression techniques to be 0.34 which indicates the effectiveness of inflation rate on the total sales index of the life insurances such that increasing the inflation rate by 1% increases the total sales index of life insurances by 0.34%. This implies the direct relationship between these two variables. The t statistic associated with this coefficient reflects the statistical reliability of 95%.
 - c) The next effective factor on the total sales index of life insurances is considered to be the interest rate for which the coefficient is obtained through regression techniques to be 5.42, i.e. increasing the interest rate by 1% leads to about 5.42% increase in the total sales index of the life insurances. The obtained coefficient indicates the direct relationship between these two variables.
4. While being in good agreement in theoretical terms with the theoretical principles, the obtained coefficients are statistically reliable as well. The statistical reliabilities of the regression analysis of the two t and F statistics are examined. To examine the statistical reliability of each coefficient, t statistic is used

where all the independent and effective variables on the sales of the life insurances have statistical reliability as pointed out before.

In addition to the t statistic which is used for the evaluation of each coefficient, the total regressions should have statistical reliability as well in the regression analysis. This test is called the regression overall significance or goodness of fit test in which the F statistic and chi-square distribution are used.

F statistic is equal to 7572.658 which indicates that the total regression is statistically reliable as well. Since the calculated F is larger than the F in the table with the same degrees of freedom and reliability level, the zero assumption (i.e. $H_0 : \beta_0 = \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \dots = \beta_k = 0$, where H_1 indicate at least one non-zero) is rejected. In other words, the regression overall significance has statistical reliability.

5. Considering the results of VAR, ECM, ARDL patterns, one could comment on how and with what rate the modifications occurs in the long-term using the modification coefficient in the long-term relationships i.e. ECM (-1) which is considered as a unique characteristic in such patterns. ECM (-1) coefficient is obtained to be about -0.34 which indicates the high modification rate of the model which in turn indicates the goodness of the model specifications and its proper selection.

6. The final result shows that economic risks (depression, inflation, lowering the interest rates) have been effective on the total sales index of the life insurances which are considered to show the developments in the insurance market and the signs of the pattern variables which are considered in the form of economic risks are all in accordance with the theoretical principles and have significant reliability in statistical terms.

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